

An Assessment of the determinants of Urban Informal Employment: Evidence from Central region, Ethiopia

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Abstract

Urban informal employment serves as a vital source of sustenance for workers, contributing to poverty reduction and increasing household income. This study investigates the determinants factors that select individuals' occupational choice among informal sector employment, informally employed in formal sector and owning formal employment in the Central region of Ethiopia. The study employed a cross-sectional survey, selecting a sample employee by purposive and convenience sampling methods. The study's data were examined via descriptive statistics and multinomial logistic regression methodologies. The study results reveal that gender, education level, working experience, family size, migration status and business ownership are determinants of choice of workers among three status of employment. The findings underscore the imperative for governmental interventions to improve working conditions, along with the implementation of labor regulations to guarantee workers' access to specified benefits and alleviate the socioeconomic difficulties encountered by employees in urban settings

Key words: *Informal employment*, multiple logistic models, Central region, Ethiopia

1. Introduction

The rapid urbanization in numerous developing countries is occurring concurrently with a slow growth rate of formal employment prospects, rising poverty levels, and weak institutions and municipalities (UN Hábitat, 2022). The overall consequence led to the majority of the urban workforce engaging in informal employment (Bruin et al., 2021; Emerging et al., 2024; ILO, 2021; Kitila et al., 2023). In Ethiopia, the urbanization rate stands at 5.4%, predominantly driven by rural-urban migration and the rapid growth of the urban labor force, which is the largest in Africa (CSA, 2022; ILO, n.d., 2018; UN Hábitat, 2022). Rural to urban migration is the primary catalyst of urbanization, mostly motivated by the pull factor of pursuing employment opportunities in urban areas (Chen et al., 2016; Kebede, 2023; Kitila et al., 2023). Nonetheless, the ability of the nation's cities to generate formal employment is limited. As a result, most migrants are expected to participate in informal employment (2023; UNDP, 2022).

Informal employment refers to a form of employment that is not governed by existing labor laws, social security provisions, or formal contractual agreements, resulting in a lack of job security and legal or social protections associated with the position (FES, 2023; ILO, 2013, 2018, 2022). It includes individuals informally employed within the formal sector, informal sector wage laborers, self-employed individuals (own-account workers), paid domestic workers, unpaid workers, and daily laborers (ILO, 2023; Pardo, 2023; Ulyseas, 2020). Worldwide, 58% (approximately 2 billion) of individuals aged 15 and older engage in informal employment, with 65% being self-employed and 35% being paid employees, primarily due to a lack of job opportunities in the formal sector (ILO, 2023b). Consequently, informal employment accounts for approximately 85% of the total labor force and 72% of non-agricultural workers in Africa (ILO, 2019, 2023b).

Informal work is still a big element of the economy, especially in developing countries. (IMF, 2017; Lorato et al., 2023). This kind of job fits with the fact that developing countries have a lot of workers but not enough capital. In developing countries, a large number of young people (ages 15 to 24) work in the informal sector. In fact, 87% of young men and 92% of young women are

employed in this way. (ILO, 2019). Furthermore, it alleviates poverty as it serves as a primary source of sustenance for numerous urban impoverished individuals in developing economies by providing food, generating income and wealth, supporting families, fostering entrepreneurship, and promoting innovation, as it constitutes a significant source of employment and livelihood for the urban poor (Bolarinwa & Munacinga, 2023; Desta, 2020; Etim & Daramola, 2020; ILO, 2018; Lorato et al., 2023). Indeed, the majority of workers in the informal sector (almost 80%) originate from impoverished homes in developing nations.

Similarly, informal employment is mainly employment of the last resort in Ethiopia. The proportion of non-agricultural informal employment remain high and estimated to be 34% of the country's GDP, is expected to employ 85.2% of all workers (DTDA, 2025; WB Group, 2023) The urban labor market has not yet become a dynamic engine for formal sector employment creation, partly due to segmentation of the labor mark. As such, the urban labor market is divided into three segments: the relatively privileged public sector; the private formal sector; and the large informal sector, which is mainly 'survival' than entrepreneurial for millions of the poor. In Ethiopia, around 37% of women and 18% of men are engaged in urban informal employment for pay (salary) (CSA, 2021). The informal sector continues to plays an important role in an economy, especially in the developing countries (Kebede, 2023; Lorato et al., 2023). This sector is well suited to emerging nations' factor endowment who has relatively limited capital and abundant labour, as it increases the need for unskilled and semi-skilled laborers, who are once more prevalent in developing nations, creating new jobs and revenue for households (Desta, 2020; Etim & Daramola, 2020; ILO, 2018; Lorato et al., 2023). However, informally employed individuals and enterprises face several challenges than formal employment. For example, Hoseini (2020), Ramsuraj (2020) and Tokman (1978) noted that lack of social security, factors – exploitative relationships between workers and employer, and inter firm, limited human and working capital, poor location and working condition, low productivity and low-quality products, and lack of effective implementation of labour laws and regulations are some of the challenges of informal employment.

In Ethiopia, research on informal employment has predominantly focused on the informality of self-employed enterprises (own-account enterprises) and wage-based informal employment within the informal sector exclusively. Desta, 2020; Dube et al., 2021; Lorato et al., 2023; (Personal &

Archive, 2020;Tsegay, 2022) with few studies addressing informally employed wage or salary workers in both informal and formal sectors. Furthermore, these studies were limited in scope, concentrating on the effects of informality on workers' livelihoods while neglecting factors that affect the workers' participation in informal sector, informal employment in formal sector and formal employment. Moreover, evidence indicates that the scope, characteristics, obstacles, and motivating factors of informal employment vary across nations, within distinct regions of a single country, among cities in a region, and within various neighbourhoods of the same city. (Goedele Van Den Broeck et al., 2023; UNDP, 2020). In Ethiopia, especially in the central region, little is known about this kind of work, even though it makes up a sizable portion of all employment and is a major source of income for many people(CSA, 2020). Therefore, this study aimed to address these gaps by focusing on identifying demographic and socio-economic determinants of workers;' choice among informal sector, owning informal job in formal sector and joining the formal sector.

2. Literature review

2.1. Concept and theory of informal employment

Hart's analysis says that the term "informal economy" was first used in economic writing in 1973 to denote small, unregistered businesses. Hart's, (1973) analysis shows that the phrase "informal economy" was first used in economic writing in 1973 to talk to small, unregistered businesses. He used a dualist paradigm to talk about how much money urban workers could make. He separated self-employment from wage-earning in both formal and informal revenue streams. He also said that self-employment is mostly linked to the informal sector. Since then, its idea and responsibilities have changed (Chen, 2006; ILO, 2023b).

The informal economy often encompasses income-generating activities, such as self-employment or wage labor, that are not regulated by law (ILO, 2023b; Shehu & Nilsson, 2014). The attributes, makeup, and functions of the informal sector have traditionally been debated, resulting in four primary perspectives on informality. The dualist notion posits that the labor market in developing countries is bifurcated between official and informal employment, with the two sectors being distinct and unstructured (Fields, 1975; Lewis, 1974; Shapiro & Stiglitz, 1984). The dualists contended that informal employment serves as an essential safety net (survival wage rate) for the underprivileged unable to obtain formal job that improves welfare economics (Hart, 1973;

Tokman, 1978). This approach posits that to optimize their values and circumvent constraints, economic agents selectively choose informal employment (Allingham, 1972).

The dualist perspective on the labour market posits the existence of segmentation within developing nations' labour markets, distinguishing between formal and informal employment sectors that remain separate and unintegrated (Fields, (Fields, 1975; Lewis, 1974; Shapiro & Stiglitz, 1984). This perspective defines informal employment as marginalised economic activities that function as a safety net and survival strategy for the urban poor, particularly unskilled adolescents and women who have been unsuccessful in securing formal employment or alternative income sources. They say there aren't enough official job openings, therefore a lot of individuals have to work in jobs that don't pay as well. mostly linked to the informal sector. Since then, its idea and responsibilities have changed.

Structuralist schools viewed the informal sector as a crucial element of the economy, interconnected with its counter-formal economy (employment) and originating from the capitalist or cost-minimization growth strategy of firms. Since both large and small businesses aim to make as much money as possible, this could lead small enterprises to cut labour costs, such as taxes, registration fees, and other expenditures that labour laws require. This could drive workers to leave their positions in the informal sector. Since then, its idea and responsibilities have changed (Chen, 2004; Moser, 1978).. Legalist views on informality that focus on the legal aspects of informal work that could either help or hurt informality in the job market. From this point of view, micro (small business) owners prefer to work informally to avoid bureaucratic rules and expensive formalities like time, taxes, and (M. A. Chen, 2012; Soto, 1990; World Bank, 1989). However, the parasitic position claims that without merely criticizing registration procedures, entrepreneurs chose informality depending on costs and benefits.

3. Materials and Methodology.

3.1 The study area

The research was carried out in Hosanna City, the capital of Ethiopia's central regional state, and in Butajira Town. Hossa City is one of Ethiopia's fastest-growing cities since it has a lot of

businesses and a lot of people living there. The city's quick growth, urbanization, and large number of people moving from the country to the city—about 47.1% of its population has migrated there for work—are all essential. This has caused more informal jobs to be available in the city, as well as concerns with unemployment and the rise of the informal sector (CSA, 2020; Mamo et al., 2021). Hosanna city is the capital of the central regional state and the Hadiya zone. It is also home to markets and businesses. Butajira town, which is the administrative capital of Misrak Gurage zone, is also one of the fastest-growing towns in central Ethiopia. There are a number of businesses and small-scale industries there. In central and southern Ethiopia, the city, town, and their surrounding areas also benefit greatly from service sectors including transportation, healthcare, and education. The city of Hosanna is located at 7°33'N 37°51'E, 230 kilometres south of the capital city of Addis Ababa. It has an elevation of 2340 to 2435 meters above sea level, which means it has a highland climate. The town of Butajira is at 8°7'N Latitude and 38°22'E Longitudes, with an elevation of 2,100 meters above sea level and 130 kilometres south of Addis Ababa (CSA, 2020).

3.2. Research Design

This study a descriptive cross-sectional survey design that employed a mixed research approach, and thus, the combination of both qualitative and quantitative approaches to obtain and analyze more detail data on the research problem. Creswell (2022), Mwamba & Peng (2020) and Twycross (2004) assert that mixed research design is very important for gathering data from multiple sources utilizing a variety of data acquisition techniques. Informally employed workers' characteristics, challenges they face, opportunity, the correlations between independent and dependent variables, and demographic and socioeconomic factors were all examined using descriptive study techniques.

3.3.. Population and Sampling

The study's target population consists of informally employed people (employees) in both formal and informal sectors. The administrations of Hossana City and Butajira Town lack verifiable statistics regarding the total number of informal firms and employees, as well as the related issues. Nonetheless, the researchers executed a preliminary study employing a pilot survey, observational methods, and the examination of significant documents (reports) from relevant bureaus within each sub-city. The researchers' initial investigation indicated that the prevalence of informal employment was uneven across the city's sub-cities. We used purposive and convenience sampling

methods to choose the sample participants because we don't know how many informal laborers there are in the city (Saunders & Thornhill, 2019)

Fig. 1. Location of the study area

Three kebeles from each city were purposefully chosen at first because there were a lot of informal workers and a lot of both informal and formal businesses based on a pilot survey. Second, 205 employees were chosen from the designated kebeles [Table 1](#) using the convenience sampling approach. The convenience sampling method allowed the researchers to incorporate a diverse array of personnel who were accessible, informed about the subject matter, and amenable to participating as respondents (Jenberu & Kasse, 2021). Afterward, sample size was determined using Cochran (1977) statistical formula, which is advised for large or vaguely defined target groups. Thus, the formula is outlined below, with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error; $P = 0.5$ (CSA, 2021)

$$n = \left(\frac{z^2}{e^2}\right) pq = \left(\frac{z}{e}\right)^2 p(1 - p) = \left(\frac{1.96}{0.05}\right)^2 0.5(1 - 0.5) = 384$$

Table 1 Distribution of sample employees by kebele

Kebele	Formal Employment	Formal Employment	Total
	Sample size	Percent	
Arada	80	20	
, Heto,	68	17	
Naremo	96	24	
Butajira	140	39	
Total	384	100	

3.4. Data type, sources, and collection method

The data for this study were obtained from primary and secondary sources. The primary data was collected using survey questionnaires, field observations, focus group talks, and key informant interviews. Closed and open-ended questions were designed to address the demographic and socio-economic aspects of workers, along with the retention of employees regarding the effects of urban informal employment on their livelihoods, based on inquiries derived from literature and prior research. Subsequent to the evaluation of the pre-test feedback, the definitive version of the questionnaire was disseminated to the study participants. Additionally, qualitative insights into perceptions of informality and the challenges encountered by workers were gathered through semi-structured interviews with selected employees performed by the researchers, along with focus group discussions with designated employees. The primary data was supplemented by secondary data acquired from both unpublished and published articles.

3.5. Methods of Data Analysis and Model Specification

To address the research objectives, a combination of descriptive statistics and econometric analysis was used. Descriptive statistics such as percentages, cross-tabulation, mean, and standard deviation were employed to provide an overview of the data. The econometric analysis focused on identifying the factors that influence the participation of informal employees (Hosmer, 2000).

3.5.1. An Econometric Model specification

Method of quantitative analysis, Multinomial logistic regression was employed to investigate the principal determinants of informal employment in which we set up *one equation for each logit* relative to the reference outcome. 'p' is ambiguous when there are more than two outcomes. To keep track of the different probabilities we will write $Pr(Y=S)$ for the probability of voting SV, $Pr(Y=A)$ for Ap, and so on. A note from the translator: see Stock and Watson, p. 268 (2007) or p. 308 (2012). The study will employ the Multinomiallogit model in line with earlier researchers. Following Wooldridge, Jeffery M. (2009): and Green (2003), the functional form of cumulative logit model is specified as follows:

The multinomial logit model is an extension of the binary logit model. . Our multinomial logit model for choice across S states ($s = 1, 2, 3$) in which individuals are sorted into three labour force categories, formally employed in the public or private enterprise, informally employed in the public or private sector, employed/works in the informal sector. The model allows the dependent variable to take three mutually exclusive and exhaustive values, $j=1, 2$ or 3 and is defined as follows

- Given individual specific covariates i , the probability for J choices is given by:

$$P(Y_i = S) = \frac{e^{X_j \beta_i}}{\sum_{k=1}^3 e^{X_k \beta_i}} \quad \text{Where:}$$

$Y_i = 1$ if an individual is formally employed in the public or private sector

$Y_i = 2$ if an individual is informally employed in the private sector

$Y_i = 3$ if an individual employed/works in the informal sector

X_i represents a specific explanatory variable

The parameters β_j are estimated using Econometrics software. An iterative maximum likelihood algorithm will be applied to estimate the empirical models in order to obtain asymptotically efficient parameter estimates. According to Greene (2003) the log-likelihood function for the multinomial logit model is-

$$\ln L = \sum_i \sum_j d_{ij} \ln P_{ij}$$

Where P_{ij} is the probability of individual I in state j if $d_{ij} = 1$ if $y_i = j$, 0 otherwise, $s = 0, \dots, j$

The first derivatives are:

$$d \ln L / d \beta = \sum_i (d_{ij} - P_{ij}) X_i$$

The Hessian is the second derivative i.e. $\frac{d^2 \ln L}{d^2 \beta} = -[1(1 - m)p, -p, p] X' X$

Thus, the dependent variable has three categories/outcomes. In order to facilitate understanding of the effects of the logit coefficients, marginal effects or predicted probabilities (that is, change

in predicted probability of choice of formal or informal categories of employment associated with changes in the explanatory variables) are developed on the basis of the multinomial logit model of being in each of the outcomes. Marginal effects (ME) are evaluated at the sample mean.

4. Results and Discussions

4.1. Summary of findings employing descriptive statistics

This section offers a concise overview of the demographic and socio-economic profile of employees, encompassing gender, age, education, marital status, family size, migration status, living arrangements, working hours, work experience, salary, family income, and access to training. Since the data used to analyze the determinants of informal employment were obtained from a survey of 384 workers which was done in 2020/25 in two urban areas namely, Hossana city and Butajira town. Regarding with the type of employment 23% of Employees holding informal job in the informal sector or an economy that is not registered, regulated, taxed, monitored by any form of government, 37% of Employees holding formal jobs in public administration and state owned enterprises or formal private enterprises, and 40% are holding informal jobs in the formal private sector enterprises that means the workers are employed without fulfilling criteria that is stated by existing labour legislation such as, formal contractual arrangements, social protection arising from the job. The result of the study indicates that a large number of workers engaged in the formal sector have an informal status

The sample comprises around 45% male workers, with the remaining 55% being female. A greater proportion of females than males in the labor market are likely to possess informal employment in the informal sector, with approximately 65% of female workers and 56% of male workers engaged in such roles. Nonetheless, the proportion of workers with formal employment is higher among males, at approximately 66%. A majority of the sampled labor force is unmarried (60%), with the largest percentage among workers in the informal sector, followed by those with informal jobs in the informal sector and those with formal jobs (about 70%, 60%, and 60% respectively). The data in Source: Own field survey,2025

shows that almost all of the respondents attended informal or formal education, indicating the employees under the survey at least they can read and write. Of the total sample respondents, about 20 percent of respondents have completed primary education, 20 percent of them have secondary

education, 5 percent of them have vocational diplomas (TVT) level of schooling, and a 5 percent of them attended a university degree and above. Source: Own field survey,2025

illustrates that there is quite difference between formal and informal employees regarding the level of education. About 76 percent of formal employees attended a technical or vocational diploma (TVT), or a university degree, it is only 60% and 43%, of informal employees attended a technical or vocational diploma (TVT), or a university degree in formal and informal sectors respectively, indicating employee with lower education attainment tend to participate in informal employment compared with formal employment. Studies demonstrate that formal employment correlates with higher educational attainment compared to informal employment (Harris-Todaro, 1970; Rafael La Porta and Andrei Shleifer, 2014; Sen et al. (2022)). Informality is typically defined by small-scale economic activity, simplistic technology, and low productivity, predominantly driven by lower educational levels.

Source: Own field survey,2025

indicates that around 67% of respondents are migrants from rural regions, whereas 44% are residents of metropolitan areas. In comparing employment types based on the migration status of employees, approximately 67% of informal workers in the informal sector and 57% in the formal sector are migrants from rural areas, whereas 44% of formal employees are migrants. This suggests that rural-urban migrants are more likely to be informal workers than rban local workers. This is in line with the studies by Tsegay & Gezahegne (023) and UNDP (2022)., which found that not many workers are moving to cities and that Ethiopian cities don't have enough jobs to offer formal employment. This means that informal work acts as a safety net for migrants. The survey results shown in Source: Own field survey,2025

indicate that the majority of sampled employees (75%) reside in rented accommodations, followed by those living with their families (25%) and those owning their homes (5%). A majority of individuals residing in their own homes are employees with official employment (95 percent). This indicates that it is challenging for nearly all employees, particularly informal workers, to reside in their own homes. Only 3% of formal employees belong to a trade union, whereas no informal workers are affiliated with any union. Unions substantially augment workers' bargaining power with employers to raise both remuneration and non-wage benefits(Cho & Cho, 2014).

Table 3 on the other hand, shows that the average age of the employees who were surveyed is about 29 years old. People who work informally are around six years younger than those who work formally. The average age of people who work informally in the formal sector is 26.5 years, and the average age of people who work informally in the informal sector is 26.96 years. This aligns with the observation that in Ethiopia, informal employment serves as the primary source of

Table 2 Summary of descriptive statistics (categorical variables)

Variables	Measure	Formal	Informal in formal	Informal sector
		Percent	Percent	Percent
Sex	Male	66	44	35
	Female	34	56	65
Marital status	Single	51	60	70
	Married	46	38	27
	Others	3	2	3
Education level	Primary school	10	18	22
	Secondary school	15	22	35
	College/TVT	21	33	24
	University and above	54	27	19
Migration status	Migrant	44	57	67
	Non-migrant	56	43	23
Living arrangement	Own home	23	2	3
	Rented (=2)	44	63	62
	With parent	33	35	35
Union member	Yes	4	0	0
	Mo	96	100	100
Written contract	Yes	100	15	5
	No	0	85	95

Source: Own field survey,2025

livelihood for the rapidly expanding urban youth labor force, given the scarcity of legitimate job opportunities (CSA, 2022; UN Hábitat, 2022; UNDP, 2022). Formal employees work an average of 44 hours a week, whereas informal employees work an average of 51 hours a week. This means that informal laborers work about 23% longer than formal workers. The results show that informal workers worked a lot of extra hours yet were paid less than formal workers. The average monthly wage of informal workers is 3,673 birrs, which is roughly 26% less than the average monthly salary of official workers, which is 4,903 birrs. Also, informal workers have about 3 years of job experience, while formal workers have about 6 years of work experience. This is in line with the fact that most informal workers are young.

Table 3 Descriptive statistics for continuous variable

Variable	Formal		Informal in formal		Informal sector	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Age	31.8	7.01	26.5	7.71	26.96	7.23
Working hour	44	4.6	50	6.8	52	1.41
Work experience	6.8	3.20	4.1	3.70	4.51	2.26
Salary	4900	2109	3673	2207	3595	2212

Source: Own field survey,2025

4.2. Multinomial logistic regression result

A multinomial logit model is used to explain the reasons employment choice each level is interpreted as a ‘category’ of the dependent variable in the model. The marginal effects represent effect of the explanatory variables on the probability of working in informal sector and informally employed in formal sector employment relative to the probability of having formal job. The estimated coefficients of the model are listed in Table 4 below. The Likelihood-Ratio test¹ provides more general support for our model (χ^2 statistic of 263.85 and associated p-value=0.000) and Pseudo-R² is calculated as 0.5586, which is an acceptable value. The estimated coefficients in Table 4 represented probability of selecting any of the three categories of participation shown in the table, with participation in the owning a formal job as the base category.

The result of multinomial logit model is put in the appendix. The sex variable has a negative coefficient and is statistically significant at 1% significant levels in the two sectors as it is shown

in Table 4. Its marginal effects are negative for the workers who are working in informal sector and owning informal job in formal sector (by just about 15% and 26%, respectively). This shows that being female as opposed to being male enhances the likelihood of being employed in informal sector and owning informal job in formal sector. This is in line with the report by Jobs CSA (2020) and (ILO, 2023), which found that the formal labor market predominantly comprises men, but the informal sector is primarily constituted of women who favor flexible work hours due to greater familial obligations, such as pregnancy and marriage. In developing nations, boys derive greater advantages from education compared to girls, resulting in increased challenges for women in securing official employment, so rendering them more susceptible to informal work

Education is significant for employment choice having informal job in formal sector and owning informal job in informal sector at 1% significant levels. There is negative relationship between education and being informally employed in formal sector and informal sector. This indicates a markedly low degree of educational attainment (human capital) among informally employed workers, illustrating that job informality is associated with diminished educational levels, in alignment with the findings of (Lemma & Sharma, 2025). In this sector, the marginal effect of education are about 16% and 13% owning informal job in formal sector and in informal sector respectively, Thus implies the higher the level of education the lower the probability of an employee to choose informal employment in both sector.

The coefficient and marginal effect of the migration status variable is positive and significant at 1% significant level for both working in informal sector and having informal job in formal sector (by just about 17% and 24%, respectively) relative to being formally employed. This suggests that rural-urban migrants are more inclined to engage in informal work than local urban workers, supporting prior studies (Tsegay & Gezahegne, 2023; UNDP, 2022) that identified the lack of formal employment opportunities in Ethiopian urban regions as a driving force for migrant workers to seek informal employment, which acts as a safety net for them. There are positive coefficient and marginal effect of 10% and 37% for the working in informal sector and owning informal job in formal sector, respectively) relative to owning formal job (negative coefficient and marginal effect of 47%) for hours of work. This variable is significant 1% level for all category and indicates that workers owning informal job works more time than formally employed workers

The coefficient and marginal effect of the experience variable is negative and significant at 5% and 1% significant level for the informally employed in formal sector and working in informal sectors sector (by just about 4.2% and 7.1%, respectively), suggesting that informal employees possess less years of professional experience than their formal counterparts. Family size is significant at the 1% level of significant and has positive effect on reasons of working in informal sector. the marginal effect of family size are about 12% and This indicates that the probability of being working in informal sector increases as the family size increase by one. It shows that when employees' families grow, they are more likely to work informally in cities. The larger the family, the less likely it is that an individual will be able to do family jobs and share family resources, especially for people who move from rural to urban areas.

Table 4 Multinomial Logistic regression estimates of the factors influencing participation of employees in urban informal employment

Variables	Formal		Informal in formal		Informal sector	
	(dy/dx)	P-value.	(dy/dx)	P-value.	(dy/dx)	P-value.
Sex	-.260***	0.003	-.145***	0.001	.406***	0.001
Age	.042	0.183	.130 **	0.014	-.173*	0.086
Marital status	.087	0.424	-.016	0.777	-.071	0.461
Education	-.163***	0.001	-.037***	0.003	.201***	.000
Living arrangement	.123	0.167	.057	0.159	-.181*	0.061
Family size	-.046	0.564	.115***	0.016	-.069	0.358
Experience	-.042***	0.040	-.071***	0.003	.112***	0.017
Migration status	-.244***	0.000	-.173***	0.000	.418***	0.000
sector	-.052	0.170	-.012	0.257	.064	0.174
Town/city	-.018	0.689	-.012	.638	.051	0.670

$N = 384$, LR $\chi^2(13) = 263.84$, $\text{Prob} > \chi^2 = 0.0000$, Log likelihood = -104.262 , Pseudo $R^2 = 0.5586$. *** and ** indicate the 1 % and 5 % significance level, respectively

5. Conclusion

In developing countries, informal employment is a substantial source of employment and income for laborers. The main aim of this paper was to revisit the factors that select individuals' occupational choice among informal sector employment, informally employed in formal sector and owning formal employment. The study covered a total of 384 selected workers. We examined the determinants of employment status in the study area and identify the application of labour law, perception of workers, constraints and risk in the working environment. Data were collected on socio-economic and demographic characteristics of respondents. The study findings clearly indicate that main factors such as gender, education level, working experience, family size, migration status and business ownership are determinants of choice of workers among three status of employment. Considering the cities/towns of workers, we observe that all of the marginal effects of three cities/towns are statistically insignificant. Government and other concerned institutions should monitor the implementation of the labour legislation and law established in Ethiopia (Labour proclamation no. 1156/2019) that gives for workers the right to work under satisfactory, safe and healthy conditions and to receive equal pay for equal work without discrimination of any kind, guarantees workers rest, leisure and reasonable limitation of working hours, public holidays with pay and remuneration, guarantees the right to form or join a trade union for the protection of their interest. Educational achievements, gender imbalance has to be addressed as a way of increasing professionalism of women and to emancipate them from being preys of informal employers.

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